

The Role of Voters' Education Programme on the Peaceful Conduct of Elections in Nigeria

By

Abdulhamid Bashir Aminu

Department of Social Development, School of Rural Technology and Enterpreneurship
Development Rano,
Kano State Polytechnic
GSM: 08028415138; 08096212088; 08056373625
abashiraminu@yahoo.com, bashirabdulhamid76@gmail.com

Halima Mansur Chiranchi

Kano State Polytechnic

School of Rural Technology and Enterpreneur Development, Rano
Department of Community Development and Adult Education
Gsm: 08028714531, 08031804114
Email: Halimawaziri.hm@gmail.com

&

Sadiq Salisu Umar

Department of Adult and Non-formal Education
School of Adult and Special Needs Education
Federal College of Education Kano
GSM: 08038117518, 08092822555
sadiqumar2323@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper provides an overview of election process and what necessitate the need for voters' education programme in Nigeria. The paper discusses the concept of election, voter education, forms of voter education and the providers of voter education programmes. It also examines the factors affecting peaceful elections, relevance of voters' education on peaceful conduct of elections and the impact of voter education in Nigeria. The paper concludes that it is obvious that peace education, citizenship education and election literacy are applicable as types of voter education programmes needed to be provided to Nigerian citizens. Hence, the content of voter education covers lessons and awareness of voting procedures, does and don'ts of election, causes and consequences of violence and conflict before, during, and after election, the delivery method which include print media, electronic media and social media, rallies, campaign in public gathering and drama shows. The impact of voter education programme help electorate to vote appropriately, encourage ethical voting and reduce the wastage of resources, increase voters turnout and increase the level of understanding of democracy among electorate. Recommendations made by this paper include; the Independent National Electoral Commission INEC should liase with adult literacy education centres to incorporate voter education

programmes into their curricular; so that the content should go beyond mere accumulation of knowledge about political structure and processes, the Federal and State government should involve community and stakeholders in mobilization and enlightenment of the general public to participate in the voter education programme.

Keywords: Election, Voter Education, Election Violence, and Peaceful Election

Introduction

The post covid-19 era in Nigeria has witness the sixth republic election period which is expected to hand over the administration to the newly electorate in 2023. This period is coupled with election processes ranging from registration of political parties, primary elections, and general elections. Yet, there is development in the utilization of information communication technology (ICT). This however, necessitate the government in Nigeria to provide various voters' education programmes targeted at mobilizing, enlightening and educating the general public on how to effectively register to participate in the coming elections in 2023. Election is an important process towards democratic strengthening. Election plays the indispensable role of stimulating and facilitating nation-building through good governance. Yet, as vital and significant as election is to nations, usually it is accompanied by malpractices and misconducts, more often, violence and conflicts with its displeasing impact especially in developing countries of the world including Nigeria (Ibrahim and Ibeanu, 2009).

Voter apathy toward vote buying and vote selling has taken a center stage in Nigerian election and which poses threat to democratic survival. Political competitors in this regard employed illicit method including bribery and corruption, fraud, and misconduct by election tribunals. Recently in the various party primaries, exchange of foreign currencies with votes is reported in Nigeria. Voter education is the type of education that instructs the citizen on the exact procedure to follow as they conduct themselves through the voting process at the poll. It may also provide

information on the intricacies of the electoral system. Voter education focuses more specifically on the role of citizen as a voter. This will include knowledge around several issues including the duty and obligation of voter, voting procedure, political parties and candidate, electoral offence, counting procedure, the responsibility of election management body and mandate protection. Indeed, voter education is design to equip citizens with knowledge about the entire gamut of the electoral process (Nkwachukwu and Orji, 2014). The five cardinal objectives of voter education is to enable voters make well inform decision about impending election, become knowledgeable and enthusiastic about the coming election, provide information about the electoral process, promote positive action and inform them about the significance of election and why they should participate in it (EKN,2014). The idea of voter education is a global phenomenon which evolves to assist in delivering free, fair, efficient and cost effective election, acceptance of result, tolerance of competition and opposition and overcome the inadequacies in administrative preparation for an election.

Since elections in Nigeria have always been characterized or marred by voter apathy, crisis, violence, rigging in various ways and the outcome appear debatable and suspicious in many cases. This has the tendency to inflict enormous disadvantages in the polity, leadership and also has negative effects on the economy and national development. Voters in Nigeria seem to lose confidence in the electoral process and this is why there is always feared and confusion when an election is in view. Some of these instances were justified by Nigeria Election Violence Report which revealed that 18 persons were killed in the South-East and 530 persons suffered varying degrees of injury during the 2019 general elections (Silk, 2020). The report which was presented by one of the non-governmental organizations that monitored the election, Women's Aid Collative, in partnership with the International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES), gave

the breakdown of the figures as follows: “one person was killed in Enugu State; six killed in Imo State; two killed in Anambra State while nine persons were killed in Ebonyi State” (Ogbonna, 2019). Complement to this, elections in all the 36 States of the Federation witnessed violence, killings, and destruction of property. It was reported that 18 cases of violence were recorded in Enugu State, while 32 of such cases were recorded in Abia State, 84 cases of violence were recorded in Imo State, out of which six people were killed while 306 people were injured. Anambra State, recorded 27 cases of violence, out of which two people were killed and 18 people injured. On the other side, Ebonyi State recorded 124 cases of violence, out of which nine people died and 91 people were injured (Ochie, 2019). However, in the North West; Kano State also witnessed a large scale of vote-buying and voter-intimidation and political hooliganism among youth that led to destruction of life and properties. All these anti-democratic acts, unarguably, call for serious voter education to remedy the situation across the States and local government areas in Nigeria.

In order to alleviate this fear and re-ignite or restore confidence about the electoral process in the minds of voters and to satisfy the bearings of local, national and international observers, credibility of the electoral process is needed to ensure the sustenance of democracy. Voter education is however conceived and introduced as means to share knowledge, information and ideas, as well as inculcate values, attitude, and skills among electorates (voters) so as to vote freely, fairly and in an orderly manner as well as respect the citizenship and civic rights of fellow voters and defend their own rights. This paper therefore discusses the role of voters’ education programme on the peaceful conduct of elections in Nigeria.

Concept of Election

The term election refers to the formal decision making process by which population chooses an individual to hold public offices. It is an “act a process of choosing” someone for a political office by voting” election is a form of procedure recognized by rule of an organization, when by all or some of the number of organization chooses a smaller number of person or persons to hold office or authority in an organization. Encyclopedia of social science (1972:1) election is a democratic process of who govern a particular group, society a state.

The genesis of elections could be traced to the ancient Greece and ancient Rome to select rulers such as the Italy Roman Empire and the Pope. Characteristics of election include: - Suffrage (the question of who may vote), Nomination, Electoral system, scheduling and election campaign. Categorically, election is of three types.

- i. General Election – this is usually an election held at regular interval, in which candidates are elected in all or most constituencies or electoral districts of a nation.
- ii. Referendum – this is a direct popular vote on proposed law or constitutional amendment.
- iii. Primary Election – this is a preliminary election to select a political candidate of a political party.

The Concept of Voter Education

Voters’ education which entails election literacy and emphasise the role of voter as essential in electoral process in ensuring a responsive, accountable and democratically elected government has in its content; concepts such as link between basic human right and voting right, the roles, responsibilities and rights of voters, the relationship between election and democracy, conditions necessary for elections, why each vote is important, types of election, date, time and place of

voting, registration requirement, mechanism for voting etc. Voter education equips the electorates with necessary information that educate them on their right to select the candidate of their choice. It contains vital aspect like when, where to register and vote casting (ECI, 2016). Election Management Bodies (EMBs) organise regular voters' education updates or broadcasts through messages, aired on radio and the print media. The EMBs modify its operation to be in tune with contemporary media trends for example, the maximum use of the internet. Elections cannot be generally said to be credible unless the voters are aware of the right choice. In addition, detailed information on voting methodology should be available ahead of time of Election Day. Voters' education activities could be directed by either the EMBs or other stakeholders like the civil society in disseminating information on what is required of the electorates throughout the electioneering process (Oduola, Hassan, and Sawaneh, 2020).

However, voter education is not limited to knowledge as a cognitive orientation. It also encompasses affective and evaluation orientations. In fact, following Almond and Verba (1989) voters' education we can argue that civic and voter education is the inculcation in the citizen, of positive orientation towards democratic structures and objects at the cognitive, affective and evaluative levels. By cognitive orientation is meant "knowledge of and belief about" democracy and specifically, the electoral process. Affective orientation refers to feelings, particularly confidence and level of trust in the electoral process, while evaluative orientation has to do with the judgments of the citizens towards democracy and the electoral process. These orientations could be towards the system as a whole, towards input objects, towards output objects and towards the self as a democratic object. Regarding input and output objects, the positive orientation may be towards roles, structures, incumbents or policies (Almond and Verba, 1989: 14-15).

Table 1 Indicative Dimensions of Voter Education

	System as general object	Input objects	Output objects	Self as object
Cognition	‘Knowledge of the electoral legal framework and belief that they can deliver free, fair and’ credible elections	Knowledge of the functions and roles of the Election Management Body (EMB) like INEC and belief that it is adequately structured to deliver free, fair and credible elections	Knowledge of the electoral adjudication process and the roles of various agencies in it.	Knowledge of one’s role in the electoral process voter, poll worker, candidate, etc.
Affect	Feeling of confidence and trust in democracy and the electoral system <i>per se</i> , not just as means to welfare ends like jobs, etc.	Feeling of confidence and trust in the EMB and other agencies involved in the conduct of elections	Feeling of confidence and trust in the judiciary and other agencies involved in electoral adjudication	Confidence in one’s capacity to make a difference
Evaluation	Judgment that the electoral system is strong and that democratic governance is guaranteed	Judgments that the EMB and other agencies are doing enough to guarantee free, fair and credible elections	Judgments that the judiciary and other agencies are effective.	Judgments that one’s participation is important and could lead to i improvements in the electoral process and democratic governance

Sources: Adapted from Almond and Verba, 1989:15

According to Ibeanu and Mbah, 2012 voter education is very critical in building voter confidence and has being implemented by wide variety of organisations and individuals. It is supported and sponsored by election administrators and democratically elected government. Voter education programmes were carried out through various agencies and offices; constitutionally established bodies; such as Human Right Commission and Intensified Regional and Domestic Civil Society Organisations, and contestants in the election (Ibrahirn, 2006). However, what is missing in our

contemporaries is the involvement of corporate bodies in its policy, planning, implementation and technical support. Example in USA, the kids voting project raised \$12 million in cash and kind from private sectors in 1998 which is seen as a substantial amount to sponsor and provide equipments for the participation in the teaching and learning strategy among voters. The facilitators role would create enabling environment for exchange of ideas such that voter has to be informed, resourceful and flexible. Also, voter education need to be supplemented by ongoing civic education because it employs a broader perspective than voter education and concern with whole citizens rather than voters alone. Furthermore, marginalised communities would be well targeted so also special groups, IDPs and other hard to reach communities (Ibrahirn, 2006).

Dominant Strategies/Approaches to Voter Education

- a) Public enlightenment
- b) Stake holders engagement
- c) Integration and implementation of voter education in secondary school and tertiary institution
- d) Institutionalization of (NIACVE) National Interagency Committee on Voter Education

Types of Voters' Education Programmes

Voter education is a type of adult education program and adult education programmes are non-formal in nature. Non formal education is the type of education that is not guided by a plan curriculum. Therefore, voter education may not have specific types or area of coverage. This is line with (EKN, 2014) that the scope of voter education programmes in any country will depend upon or variety of factors. The following types of programmes can be effectively applied in Nigeria:

- i. Civic education is broadly defined as inculcating in citizens those “skills, values and behaviours that are thought to be necessary for a stable and effective democracy” (USAID, 2002). According to USAID, its broad goals are threefold:
 - a. To introduce citizens to the basic rules and institutional features of democratic political systems and to provide them with knowledge about democratic rights and practices;
 - b. To convey a specific set of values thought to be essential to democratic citizenship such as political tolerance, trust in the democratic process, respect for the rule of law, and compromise; and
 - c. To encourage responsible and informed political participation; defined as a cluster of activities including voting, working in campaigns, contacting officials, lodging complaints, attending meetings, and contributing money (Ibid).

It is however becomes necessary for the stakeholders in the education sector to encourage the participation of faith based organisations and community based organisations in the development of curriculum for civic education in our societies.

- ii. Peace education is being considered by various scholars to be both a philosophy and a process involving multiple skills including conflict resolution and cooperation, holding patience, calm listening, problem solving as well as reflection along with empowering of people with appropriate knowledge to create a safe rather better world with a resilient environment as it fosters non-violence, love and compassion and reverence for all the lives. Peace education in UNICEF refers to the process of promoting the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to bring about behavior changes that will enable the children, youth and adults to prevent conflict and violence, both overt and structural; to resolve conflict peacefully; and to create the conditions conducive to peace, whether at an

intrapersonal, interpersonal, intergroup, national or international level (Mukherjee and Biswas, 2017).

These justified that no matter what a society is, peace education is a tool for promotion of social economic and political development.

- iii. Computer literacy is referred to the knowledge and capabilities of an individual to make use of computers and other technologies in an efficient manner. Computer literacy can also take into account the comfort level of the individuals that they have in making use of computer literacy programmes and applications.
- iv. Election literacy, in its context is an aspect which deals with provision of knowledge to voters or citizens on the right to vote and or contest in the elections. Becoming literate here signifies that voters will be literate on the processes involved during elections as provided in the constitution and electoral acts.

Providers of Voters' Education

Voter education is implemented by wide variety of organization and individuals. It is supported and sponsored by election administrators and democratically elected government through various agencies and offices. In Nigeria, Section 2 (a) and (b), as well as Section 154 of the Electoral Act 2010 establish the power of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) to conduct voter and civic education. According to Section 2 of the Act, "In addition to the functions conferred on it by the Constitution, the Commission shall have power to: (a) conduct voter and civic education. (b) Promote knowledge of sound democratic election processes". This legal power of the Commission has often been interpreted to mean that the Commission has a principal responsibility to conduct voter and civic education. Consequently, other traditional

agencies of civic and voter education expect the Commission to take the lead on this. Over the years, the Commission has been increasing its budgetary allocation to voter education. For the 2015 general elections, for instance, the Commission plans to spend 1% of the estimated budget of 93 billion Naira, which translates into about ₦930 million, on voter education. In spite of this growing budgetary outlay on voter education, the impact on knowledge of voters remains unclear. This raises a number of questions regarding the capacity of the Commission to conduct civic and voter education on its own, the appropriateness and reach of materials, the adequacy of the strategies adopted. It also raises the issues of burden sharing and above all the need to understand how voter and civic education is carried out in other countries.

The history of democratic elections in Nigeria especially ones that would be adjudged and accepted by the electorates as free and fair had always been a problem in the country. In 1960, shortly after Nigeria's independence there was a transition from the colonial rule to the country's First Republic election process. However, it is common knowledge that Nigeria's electoral process has persistently come short the glory of what the electoral process should mean for a democratic society. Nigerian electoral history has not been a pleasant one. Nigerians have participated in many elections, beginning with the colonial era when the concept of elections was first introduced.

Factors Affecting Peaceful Elections in Nigeria

There are many factors that affect peaceful conduct of elections. Some of these factors are as follows:

1. Electoral Process and Procedures

- a) The electoral process and procedures should go well with biracial compliance with electoral regulations.

- b) Electoral officials and materials should arrive at polling unit on time and voting environment should be well laid out with supporting infrastructure.
- c) Election observers, party and security agents should not be intrusive. Their conduct should be matured and professional.
- d) Voters should be orderly. These factors together with enhanced smart card reading will boast success of accreditation exercise.
- e) The actual phase of voting should start on time and it should be peaceful.
- f) Voters should not be disenfranchised as a result of early closure accreditation and commencement of voting a head of INEC stipulated time.

2. Voters and Political Party behavior

Voters' education is the act or response of electorate into politics based on

- a) Voter's turnout should be made through. This should be made possible by avoiding tense electoral environment across the country including pre-electoral violence.
- b) False assumption that the desire for change would not be attained, should be cleared and that their votes would not influence the final outcome.
- c) The conduct of political parties should be satisfactory. There should be no cases of hijacking of electoral materials and there should be no disruption of electoral process.

3. Violence and Conflicts

Violence is defined by Dode, (2010) as any act, which cause or may cause any person physical, psychological, emotional, sexual, verbal or economic harm, whether it occur in private or in public, in peace time or conflict situation. In electoral process, violence is any act perpetrated in the cause of political activities including pre, during and post election period and may include, any of the following act, thuggery, use of force to disrupt political meeting and voting at polling stations, use of dangerous weapons to intimidate voters and other election process, or to cause

bodily harm or injury to person or persons. To have a peaceful conduct of election, violence of any kind should be avoided in the electoral process.

4. Conduct of Security Agents

Generally, the conducts of security agents have great and positive impact on the electoral process. Apart from providing security for movement of INEC officials and materials, their interventions in many areas facilitate peaceful conduct of the exercise. Security agents should not be found disrupting the exercise engaging in fraud. There should be no harassment and intimidation of people. They should not maintained passive disposition in the face of clear breaches of electoral procedures.

Regarding factors responsible for peaceful conduct of elections, the former INEC chairman Professor Jega, in 2015 added that ‘there is need for honest, competent and non-partisan administration to run election (Ibeanu, 2007). Other studies have shown that there are more factors pre requisite for peaceful conduct of election which include:

- ❖ Various national and international observers should come up with report devoid of ambiguity which should be of benefit. Such report should help to improve in areas not well articulated.
- ❖ The various electronic gadgets should be functional and active.
- ❖ Electorates on their part should be calm, cool and to face any intimidation on the election-day.
- ❖ The press should play the vital role of deep democracy and enlighten the mind of people by improving their rational and social being.

Relevance of Voters' education on Peaceful Conduct of Elections

In principle, voter education will enable voters to make well informed decisions about impending elections, become knowledgeable and enthusiastic about the coming election, explain the essence of democracy, motivate voters into positive action and inform them about the significance about election and why they should participate in it. However, voter education is critical element in building voter confidence hence it provides the background attitude, behavior and knowledge among citizens that stimulate and consolidate democracy during election, the election will ensure effective organization by citizens in support of parties and cause behavior by citizens that is appropriate to a peaceful election, acceptance of result, tolerance of conception and opposition. It also assists in delivery of free and fair, efficient and cost effective election. Furthermore, it is believed that voter education overcome inadequacies in administrative preparation for an election. Generally it increases voters turn out thereby providing a framework for protecting, sustaining and institutionalizing a culture of credible election and popular participation in governance (Ibrahim, 2004).

The Impact of Voter Education

There are many ways in which voter education impact on lives of people especially voters. These impacts are as follows:

- a. It enables the voter to make well informed decision about impending election
- b. It enables voter become knowledge and enthusiastic about elections
- c. It provides information about the electoral process
- d. It provides positive attitude to election
- e. It explains the essences of democracy

- f. It motivates voter into positive action about importance of election and why he/she should participate in it
- g. It helps in acceptance of election result and tolerance
- h. It tells the importance of each vote and the impact on public accountability
- i. It gives knowledge about right, roles and responsibilities of votes.

Conclusion

It is obvious that peace education, citizenship education and election literacy are applicable as types of voter education programmes needed to be provided to Nigerian citizens. Hence, the content of voter education covers lessons and awareness of voting procedures, does and don'ts of election, causes and consequences of violence and conflict before, during, and after election, the delivery method which include print media, electronic media and social media, rallies, campaign in public gathering and drama shows, the impact of voter education programme, it help electorate to vote appropriately, encourage ethical voting and reduce the wastage of resources, increase voters turnout and increase the level of understanding of democracy among electorate.

Recommendations

- i. The Independent National Electoral Commission INEC should liase with adult literacy education centres to incorporate voter education programmes into their curricular; so that the content should go beyond mere accumulation of knowledge about political structure and processes. It should also include ability to process and interpret information as activist citizenship and significant judgment,

- ii. The Federal and State government should involve community and stakeholders in mobilization and enlightenment of the general public to participate in the voter education programme, and
- iii. INEC at the Federal and State levels should engage all stakeholders in the design and implementation of voters' education programmes so as to arrest some of the problems being faced in the process.

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